

Multimodal Pipelines for Search and Discovery

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Abstract: We present a formalization of competing approaches—CLIP and Multimodal Language Models (MLLMs)—for the search and discovery of large digitized archives of visual materials. Qualitative and quantitative comparisons of these two approaches are presented along with forward-looking questions to guide continued research in this area.

1. Background

A shared goal of both scholars and archivists working with large visual collections has been to replicate the modalities of search and discovery interfaces that have existed for textual collections since the early days of computing [6, 24, 49, 50, 51]. Specifically, once a collection of textual documents has been converted into a digital format, it is straightforward to provide a basic search interface that surfaces texts containing particular words or phrases of interest [8]. Additional refinements based on this approach can improve the usability of the results by allowing for morphological variations of words, searching across synonyms, and providing importance scores to sort the results. How can we similarly approach digitized collections of visual materials? Until recently, the only accessible search options were to use structured metadata fields such as hand entered captions and provenance information. These limitations significantly limited the ability to access digital collections of visual materials, particularly as digitization efforts produced increasingly large collections that outpaced the ability for archivists to fully describe all of the elements with customized descriptions.

The deep learning revolution of the late aughts fueled by algorithmic and hardware advances provided a new opportunity for working with large collections of digital images [14, 40, 20, 40]. In the span of less than a decade, computer vision researchers moved from working with small thumbnail icons with thousands of pixels to widely accessible algorithms that were able to reliably generate meaningful tags on high-resolution images [13, 32]. Working from large-scale challenges such as ILSVRC and MS COCO, open-source models such as VGG19, YOLO, and Fast R-CNN allowed for the automatic tagging of images for a set of commonly found objects, faces, and other meaningful elements. These elements were able to be incorporated into search interfaces allowing for directly searching specific images tagged with the objects contained in these datasets [17]. Furthermore, by deconstructing the deep learning models behind these approaches, it became possible to generate image embeddings [15, 16]. These mathematical objects allow for associating any image with a sequence of numbers such that objects sharing similar visual features will have similar sequences of numbers [36]. Image embeddings allowed deep learning models to be extended to finding similar clusters of images that extended beyond existing categories and could be applied to collections of digitized images such as paintings, material arts, and other non-photographic collections [30, 31]. These approaches opened exciting new possibilities for exploring large visual collections and were successfully applied in a number of well-known archival public projects. However, the limitations of these techniques still fell short of the straightforward search and discovery techniques available for exploring collections of textual documents [2, 3, 4, 35, 37, 41].

2. Multimodal Pipelines

Over the past several years, a new wave of multimodal models have been developed that offer the potential for search and discovery interfaces for visual collections that fully mirror those available for textual collections [21, 25, 26, 27, 39, 55]. By combining textual data with visual data, Multimodal models intrinsically pair images with explicit textual descriptions of the

semantic information contained within the visual material [43, 54]. The close linkage between text and image makes it possible to build interfaces that search a visual collection through textual descriptions [48]. While often combined under the common description of ‘multimodal models’, two distinct and conceptually different approaches exist. In the remainder of this paper, we formalise the differences between these approaches and evaluate them empirically and theoretically through a case study of a collection of historic photographs from the 1970s.

The neural network Contrastive Language-Image Pre-Training, known as CLIP, is a multimodal model that was one of the first approaches to combine text and image inputs [38]. The CLIP-family of models, which include newer, more accurate models such as SigLIP, share a similar structure that can be described compactly using a simple mathematical notation. Let \mathcal{I} be the set of all possible images and \mathcal{T} be the set of all possible texts within one or more languages. For some fixed embedding dimensionality n , CLIP models learn a pair of functions f and g such that

$$\begin{aligned} f &: \mathcal{I} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n \\ g &: \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n. \end{aligned}$$

The model is trained to have $f(i)$ be close to $g(t)$ whenever t is a textual description of the image i . Using a CLIP-type model immediately opens a powerful approach for working with a collection of images. First, we start by computing the embeddings $f(i)$ for every image i in the collection. This allows us to build a free-text search interface by taking any search query t , computing $g(t)$, and then returning the images i that have an embedding $f(i)$ closest to the search query embedding. This approach was recently shown to be effective for studying a large collection of digitized maps [28].

A distinct second class of multimodal approaches comes from recent advances in multimodal large language models (MLLMs). We can again describe these models with a compact mathematical formula by defining \mathcal{I} and \mathcal{T} as above, with \mathcal{P} being the set of all possible prompting questions. Prompts may include both textual questions as well as additional visual elements. An MLLM can be described as a function h such that

$$h : \mathcal{I} \times \mathcal{P} \rightarrow \mathcal{T}.$$

The goal of the model $h(i, p)$ be an accurate response to the question posed by p about the input image i . A search interface for a visual collection can be built from a multimodal LLM by first selecting a fixed prompt \tilde{p} asking for a description of the image and then computing the responses $h(i, \tilde{p})$ for every image i in the collection. Textual search techniques can then be used to surface images i that have descriptions $h(i, \tilde{p})$ that share keyword(s) or phrases with any search query. The authors published a recent paper evaluating this approach [10].

3. Evaluation

Much has already been written about the accuracy of CLIP models and MLLMs. Our goal is not to replicate these papers but rather to offer a direct comparison of these two approaches applied to a search interface for an archive of visual images [22]. We took a collection of nearly 16 thousand digitized photographs from the Documerica archive (environmental documentary photographs taken by the U.S. federal government in the 1970s) and applied a CLIP model (SigLIP) and an MLLM model (GPT-4) to each of the images [1, 9, 5, 52, 56]. Then, we ran queries for a set of 90 crowd-sourced tags associated with images in the Documerica archive using both models.

For each of the 90 tags, we looked at a selection of 10 images selected by the MLLM search and

the 10-highest scored images from the SigLIP model.¹ We identified 97% of the SigLIP images to have correctly contained the target term. For the MLLM, 94% of the images contained the tag in question. Both of these results suggest that each model produces meaningful results that largely align with the crowd-sourced tags. While SigLIP has a slightly higher accuracy, the MLLM is only slightly behind even though we are taking a random subset rather than the most confident images. At a larger scale, Tables 1 and 2 show the results of all ninety tags. We see that some tags are much more common than the user-generated tags indicate (i.e., ‘window’ and various colors). Terms with multiple words in some cases show no results for the MLLM model. For single term tags other than generic colors, the MLLM usually finds something close to a superset of the images tagged by users. For SigLIP, while the top results seem accurate, the median rank of user tagged images for a given tag is often much larger than the number of images detected by the MLLM or users. This means that either the other models are missing a large number of images or that SigLIP struggles with results outside of the top ranked ones.

A further qualitative assessment of the two models can be given by looking at some individual results. In Figure 1 and Figure 2 we see images tagged with the term ‘street’ by the two models. All of the photos are accurate, but the ranking of the SigLIP model provides a better way of getting images particularly dominated by streets. The results from SigLIP for the search phrase ‘’ are shown in Figure 3 (no results are given by the MLLM), all of which accurately correspond to the query. Figures 4, 5, and 6 however, show instances where SigLIP produces false results for phrases that do not match images in the collection.²

4. Conclusions

We have formalized two different kinds of multimodal models for enhancing the search and exploration of digitized collections of visual materials. While both the CLIP-based models and MLLMs offer their own benefits and tradeoffs, we hope to have highlighted that these are significantly different approaches that need to be carefully evaluated and considered [12, 19, 33]. We have given some brief, preliminary results (as much as could fit in the space provided) showing a comparison of these approaches on one dataset. Further research and refinement in this space is needed to realise their full potential, particularly as new models from each perspective continue to be widely adopted [11, 47].

¹When there were less than 10 MLLM images, we looked only at those images that were tagged. We included a small set of proper names in the table but removed them from the summary numbers given in the paper.

²The scores of all five images from these two examples are higher than all but one of the street images in Figure ??, indicating that these can not be easily filtered out by a simple threshold technique.

Tag	User Tag #	MLLM #	MLLM Miss #	SigLIP Median
aerial view	20	1117	5	947
air pollution	20	59	20	560
seaweed	20	44	9	178
waste	20	464	9	640
woman	20	1824	5	1040
dog	19	182	0	78
rural life	19	198	17	1060
sewage treatment	19	4	16	58
shoreline	19	549	14	584
bridge	18	684	3	341
cliff	18	350	6	237
desert	18	450	9	451
environmental damage	18	11	18	930
natural resources	18	0	18	8086
pipe	18	339	6	496
sailboat	18	205	6	165
cowboy hat	17	143	7	196
epa	17	18	16	6490
hat	17	1207	2	462
home	17	536	12	2068
pine tree	17	143	10	1150
bird	16	325	3	146
dump	16	142	13	163
farmer	16	33	12	104
fog	16	201	9	161
industry	16	504	11	1190
log	16	437	4	220
wood	16	823	8	2236
coastline	15	292	3	83
fish	15	304	5	198
industrial architecture	15	52	13	1235
log road	15	0	15	959
lumber mill	15	7	15	1662
power line	15	215	8	282
recreation	15	142	14	1344
renewable energy	15	17	14	1168
sky	15	7179	1	1048
sun	15	913	3	138
bicycle	14	157	2	63
coal	14	137	13	426
girl	14	327	2	486
heat	14	78	11	3544
hillside	14	234	10	1763
pacific ocean	14	0	14	499
sewage	14	12	12	554

Table 1: First set of user-generated tags from the Documerica collection. Comparisons of the user-generated tags and the MLLM tags are shown in the first three columns of numbers. The final column shows the median position of the user-tagged images by the SigLIP score.

Tag	User Tag #	MLLM #	MLLM Miss #	SigLIP Median
solar	14	36	11	638
women	14	4	14	1543
airplane	13	93	6	44
cattle	13	67	8	62
driftwood	13	87	4	36
litter	13	347	8	496
pier	13	276	4	209
reflection	13	835	6	207
smog	13	60	12	921
smoke stack	13	3	11	250
tailing	13	10	12	359
telephone pole	13	28	13	1327
trail	13	269	6	598
window	13	2048	1	614
alpine lake	12	0	12	106
brown	12	2445	7	3830
factory	12	455	4	434
farming	12	230	4	242
fishing pole	12	10	12	165
malibu canyon	12	0	12	4106
ocean bluff	12	0	11	57
solar heat	12	2	11	145
animal	11	448	8	234
cow	11	70	2	57
deer	11	61	1	46
dirt road	11	251	7	927
family	11	303	7	609
mountain range	11	280	8	2324
seagull	11	58	2	26
yellow	11	2104	1	140
backpacker	10	1	10	64
barn	10	191	0	102
camping	10	119	2	94
chimney	10	355	8	380
construction	10	1107	2	1158
development	10	829	6	7034
fire	10	260	2	132
fur	10	102	4	46
grazing	10	20	10	33
high intensity	10	0	10	10326
highway	10	366	3	550
housing	10	158	9	400
industrial sites	10	0	10	890
land development	10	24	7	348
malibu	10	0	10	6480

Table 2: Second set of user-generated tags from the Documerica collection. Comparisons of the user-generated tags and the MLLM tags are shown in the first three columns of numbers. The final column shows the median position of the user-tagged images by the SigLIP score.

Figure 1: Random selection of five images tagged with the term 'street' according to the GPT-4 generated caption.

Figure 2: Top five images associated with the term 'street' according to the SigLIP based image embedding.

Figure 3: Top five images associated with the phrase 'men in suits talking to each other' according to the SigLIP based image embedding.

Figure 4: Top five images associated with the term 'cellphone' according to the SigLIP based image embedding.

Figure 5: Top five images associated with the phrase 'a man in a toga sitting on an elephant' according to the SigLIP based image embedding.

Figure 6: Top five images associated with the phrase ‘a very smart woman’ according to the SigLIP based image embedding. We wanted to highlight the potential challenges of placing a free search algorithm like this on a public project. While we have chosen a charged and subjective, albeit positive, query here, one could easily replace the query with a search for people with a negative personality trait. The results can quickly become an issue for the unintended connections the model makes between the query and the people surfaced in the results.

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